

BASIS OF SIMULATION TECHNIQUE FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF OPTIMAL CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING SCHEME

ОСНОВИ ТЕХНІКИ МОДЕЛЮВАННЯ ДЛЯ РОЗРОБКИ ОПТИМАЛЬНОЇ СХЕМИ СКРИНІНГУ НА РАК ШИЙКИ МАТКИ

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Cervical cancer (CC) is one of the world's deadliest forms of cancer. Incidence rates for CC during the previous decade showed an increasing trend in Ukraine, taking nowadays the 2nd place of cancers among women of reproductive age. Prevention of CC development in almost all cases of CC can be achieved by cervical screening. From an economic point of view screening strategies are evaluated through cost-effectiveness analysis. Different variations of cervical screening strategies are implemented all over the world, but their expected effectiveness for the Ukrainian population is not assessed.

Markov model for the natural history of CC was designed to analyze optimal criteria of basic cytological testing as the main tool for primary triage of women with the given precursors of CC. It describes natural transitions between health states, such as healthy, cervical intraepithelial neoplasia of 1st grade (CIN 1), cervical intraepithelial neoplasia of 2nd and 3^d grade (CIN 2/3). The first step is the parameterization of the transition probabilities matrix with the use of natural observation data. The second step, namely optimization, based on the simulation, answers how many years (cycles of the model) a woman who has been fixed in a certain condition (healthy or CIN 1) will come for the next examination. If a woman is found in state CIN2 / 3 - she has to be treated and removed from the screening model.

The basic model starts with healthy individuals and goes through k cycles. After that, persons in the CIN 2/3 state are withdrawn from the modeling system. For these ones who were identified at the first examination in a healthy state, their natural model starts again with a duration of k cycles. For these ones who were identified at the first examination in the CIN 1 state, their natural model starts with a duration of n cycles. At the end of every simulation, the CIN 2/3 state is reset to zero, and individuals in

healthy and CIN 1 states are re-included into new corresponding models depending on the current state, and so on.

That is, summing up, at the end of each Markov chain (the length of which depends on the starting state) one state is reset, and for persons in the remaining two states, new Markov chains of appropriate length will start. Visually, this is similar to the growth of the Markov chain over time as a directed graph, but the length of which in total does not exceed the observation age. At each point in time, the frequency of persons and the usefulness in each state on all branches, and the sum as a whole on the graph are calculated. Here, too, the optimization problem is finally formulated: it is necessary to find such values of k and n that the ratio of the global number of observations and the global total utility is minimal. The study provides a basic simulation-optimization technique for the development of cervical screening recommendations under the available data.